

ENDOLUMBAR OZONE-NOOTROPIC THERAPY IN WOMEN WITH INJURIES

Fuzaylova Iroda Ikromovna

Resident of the 2nd year of study in the specialty Obstetrics and Gynecology Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of the Faculty of Postgraduate Education, Samarkand State medical university, Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

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Introduction: Traumatic brain injuries and arachnoiditis are the most random case among the socially active layer of the population aged 18-40 years, and also occur in women with a special course, which indicates the relevance of this problem. Ozone therapy using the lumbar method stimulates the immune system of the human body to fight viral and other pathological processes in the human body, besides, ozone has bactericidal properties. This reduces the risk of infection and complications from the brain.

Goal: The aim of this study is to study the effectiveness of endolumbar administration of ozone and nootropics in the outcomes of traumatic brain injury and arachnoiditis in women who were hospitalized.

Materials and methods: Data are collected from 70 patients with various outcomes of TBI, aged 18 to 55 years, from the Department of Neurosurgery of Samarkand State Medical University for 2022.

All the patients were investigated by the exact same neuroimaging method and the lumbar puncture for the aspiration of the cerebrospinal fluid. The laboratory investigation of the CSF we conclude the level of the (Na, K, Fe, P, Cl, Mg) in the CSF by ROCHE -HITACHI analyzer after 1 months of treatment. Among the patient 28 (40%) patients were diagnosed with post-traumatic cerebral arachnoiditis in 29 (41%) with post-traumatic epilepsy. For the endolumbar method the ozone is blown into the lumbar region by giving the local anesthesia by the method of the lumbar puncture the endolumbar dosage of injection is according to the age of the patients.

Result: In order to find out the effectiveness of the endolumbar after the treatment we study the composition of the CSF again to see the normalize level of

the micro-macro elements presents in the CSF and bloodstream which is very necessary for the different activities of the brain. In the CSF investigation it has been shown the decreased level of Ca in 89.2% patients and the level of K, Cl is decreased in 100% of patients. The level of Na, P, Fe in the fluid were normal but the averaged amount of Na, and P were high in 41% and 86.6% patients the level of Mg were also increased in 38.6 (32) patients.

After the endolumbar ozone-nootropic treatment the level of all the micro-macro elements were normalize. After the treatment the investigation of the CSF shows the normal level of the micro-macronutrients in the blood stream and CSF.

Conclusions: An imbalance in the level of micro-macroelements in the cerebrospinal fluid can lead to various metabolic disorders and can lead to a number of neurological changes, so the introduction of ozone and nootropic treatment in the endolumbar region can normalize the level of micro-macroelements in the blood. A positive result in our patients, whom we have carried out nootropic treatment and endolumbar ozone is effective for TBI and arachnoiditis in women. The data presented by us testify to the high efficiency of the use of ozone in combination with nootropics in various diseases and give a favorable result in the immediate period of treatment.

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